

SITE	YEAR	AREA	SECTOR	ELEVATION	STRATIGRAPHICAL UNIT		
GPR	11	6		Min: 62.434 Max: 62.76	1348 <input type="checkbox"/> Natural <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Anthropropic		
In cross-section? <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No			In elevation drawing? <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No		Photos: <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No #: F47-49	Photo Model: <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No #: 299	
DEFINITION stone embankment below SU1279				Covered by <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> SU: 1279	Fills <input type="checkbox"/> SU:	Filled by <input type="checkbox"/> SU:	
HOW IS LAYER DISTINGUISHED? <input type="checkbox"/> Color <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Composition <input type="checkbox"/> Compaction			FORMATION PROCESS <input type="checkbox"/> Accumulation <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Construction <input type="checkbox"/> Cutting <input type="checkbox"/> Erosion <input type="checkbox"/> Collapse <input type="checkbox"/> Intentional deposition				
INCLUSIONS For each inclusion specify frequency: (f)requent, (m)edium, (r)are					SOIL/MATRIX		
Anthropic		Geological		Organic		clay 80% silt 15% sand 5%	
<input type="checkbox"/> Pottery <input type="checkbox"/> Nails <input type="checkbox"/> Tiles <input type="checkbox"/> Marble <input type="checkbox"/> Amphorae <input type="checkbox"/> Quarried debris <input type="checkbox"/> Dolia <input type="checkbox"/> Slag <input type="checkbox"/> Brick <input type="checkbox"/> Mosaic tile(s) <input type="checkbox"/> Basalt slabs <input type="checkbox"/> Mortar <input type="checkbox"/> Opus signinum <input type="checkbox"/> Coins <input type="checkbox"/> Painted plaster <input type="checkbox"/> Metal (specify) <input type="checkbox"/> Burnt Adobe <input type="checkbox"/> Collapse debris <input type="checkbox"/> Other (specify) <input type="checkbox"/> Glass		<input type="checkbox"/> Tufo (specify) <input type="checkbox"/> Travertine <input type="checkbox"/> Other Limestone <input type="checkbox"/> Basalt <input type="checkbox"/> Clay <input type="checkbox"/> Sand <input type="checkbox"/> Silt <input type="checkbox"/> Pebbles (range) <input type="checkbox"/> Gravel (range)		<input type="checkbox"/> Charcoal <input type="checkbox"/> Ash <input type="checkbox"/> Animal bones <input type="checkbox"/> Human bones <input type="checkbox"/> Animal teeth <input type="checkbox"/> Human teeth <input type="checkbox"/> Shells <input type="checkbox"/> Other (specify)		<input type="checkbox"/> Granular <input type="checkbox"/> Layered <input type="checkbox"/> Cohesive Compaction <input type="checkbox"/> Hard <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Compact <input type="checkbox"/> Friable <input type="checkbox"/> Loose <input type="checkbox"/> Soft	Color <input type="checkbox"/> Black <input type="checkbox"/> Brown <input type="checkbox"/> Gray <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Light Brown <input type="checkbox"/> Light Gray <input type="checkbox"/> White <input type="checkbox"/> Yellow <input type="checkbox"/> Red <input type="checkbox"/> Light Yellow <input type="checkbox"/> Other (specify)
UNIT LIMITS (also indicate on overlay)							
Northern Limit			<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Original <input type="checkbox"/> Not Original <input type="checkbox"/> Excavation Limit		Depth: <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Original <input type="checkbox"/> Not Original		
Southern Limit			<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Original <input type="checkbox"/> Not Original <input type="checkbox"/> Excavation Limit				
Western Limit			<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Original <input type="checkbox"/> Not Original <input type="checkbox"/> Excavation Limit				
Eastern Limit			<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Original <input type="checkbox"/> Not Original <input type="checkbox"/> Excavation Limit				
STRATIGRAPHICAL SEQUENCE							
Is equal to: 1398				Is bound to (only for masonry):			
Is abutted by:				Abuts: 1185			
Is covered by: 1270				Covers: 1001 bedrock			
Is cut by:				Cuts:			
Is filled by:				Fills:			
OBSERVATIONS short wall built of irregular basalt blocks. Wall is built amidst uneven bedrock, and in parts the wall is built up to meet the bedrock at its highest parts.							
DESCRIPTION							
Position within sector: wall runs south to north, in center of sector							
Shape: oblong rectangle (37cm x 540cm)							
For layers complete this section:							
Surface (slope direction: visible inclusions):							
Observations about inclusions (Clusters? Deposition slope):							
Observations about thickness (Increases? Decreases?):							
Nature of the interface with layer below: <input type="checkbox"/> sharp <input type="checkbox"/> diffuse <input type="checkbox"/> commigled <input type="checkbox"/> other (specify)							
For cuts complete this section:				Sketch for layers and/or cuts (indicate North):			
Cut edges: <input type="checkbox"/> rounded <input type="checkbox"/> straight							
Cut sides: <input type="checkbox"/> straight <input type="checkbox"/> concave <input type="checkbox"/> convex <input type="checkbox"/> sloping							
Cut bottom: <input type="checkbox"/> flat <input type="checkbox"/> concave <input type="checkbox"/> irregular							
How is cut top edge? <input type="checkbox"/> sharp <input type="checkbox"/> rounded							
How is cut bottom edge? <input type="checkbox"/> sharp <input type="checkbox"/> rounded							
Observations:							

For structural remains complete this section

Alignment: north to south

Building Technique: Adobe/Mud-brick Ashlar (blocks) Irregular (unworked) stone Concrete Other (specify)

Binding Agent: None Clay Mortar (if so, specify composition, color, compaction)

Concrete inclusions:

Material Tufo Basalt Travertine Tiles Other (specify)
 Size Small (range) _____ Medium (range) _____ Large (range) _____ Representative size: e.g. 2 x 1 x 2 cmz

Wall Facing:

Opus quadratum Opus incertum Opus reticulatum Petit appareil Opus testaceum Opus mixtum Opus vittatum Other (specify)

Complete this section for foundations Faced foundation Wooden shuttering No shuttering

floor/revetment type

Floor type: Beaten Earth Opus signinum Opus scutulatum Opus Sectile Mosaic Opus spicatum Other (specify)

Wall finishing Stucco Opus signinum Plaster Painted Plaster Other (specify)

Approx. length, width, height of structural remains:

length: 540 cm
width: 57 cm height: ~37 cm

Description:

Sketch (if applicable, indicate North) → N

INTERPRETATION

stone/sand/silt - embankment to carry sewer slabs in order to prevent the sewer being filled with soil and dirt over time

- su is not excavated

SOIL SAMPLING: Yes No

Total volume of layer (buckets):

Sample quantity (buckets):

Sample fraction (%):

NON SOIL SAMPLES: Yes No

If yes, specify (e.g. charcoal, mortar etc.):

Size:

SIEVING: Yes No

Total volume of layer (buckets):

Sample quantity (buckets):

Sample fraction (%):

STRATIGRAPHICAL RELIABILITY

Good Fair Poor

Filled-out by M. Moore

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Entered by

on